

Deliverable D1.2

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Project Acronym:	BioMedBridges	
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	Research Infrastructures, FP7 Capacities Specific Programme; [INFRA-2011-2.3.2.] "Implementation of common solutions for a cluster of ESFRI infrastructures in the field of "Life sciences"	
Deliverable title:	Devise Metrics to measure progress and impact of construction	
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WP Title	Management	
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Contributing partner(s):	2: University of Oxford (UOX) 3: Karolinska Institutet (KI) 4: Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC) 5: Heinrich-Heine Universität Düsseldorf (UDUS) 13: Vrije Universiteit (VUMC)	

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1 Executive summary

The aim of this deliverable is to provide project-wide metrics to track the progress and impact of BioMedBridges. There are different areas in the project that offer themselves to performance measurement via different, specific types of metrics:

- Grant fulfilment
- Technical metrics (data and services, tools, standards)
- Knowledge output and dissemination
- Outreach and inreach
- Training delivery and cross-RI workshops.

Metrics that will be useful for the assessment of the BioMedBridges project must meet certain criteria in addition to those for basic project metrics. To document impact of and progress within the project they must:

- enable the detection and documentation of what—in terms of technical solutions developed—works and what does not work, and which direction the development of services should take to make them truly useful for researchers
- document how RIs successfully “cluster”, i.e. move together and develop the common interfaces, technical infrastructure, and integration of the different scientific communities in order to enable metrics used for the assessment of BioMedBridges to provide powerful arguments for the project and the participating research infrastructures.

The scope and rationale of suitable metrics are laid out in this document and specific metrics, their definitions and data collection procedures are listed in the attachments.

2 Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

No.	Objective	Yes	No
1	Manage the BioMedBridges project from Year 1-4		X
2	Organise the management meetings for all the project including: the Annual General Meeting for all partners; the Executive Steering Committee meetings (up to twice per annum) and the regular meetings of the Technical Coordination Committee (up to 3 times per annum)		X
3	Organise the Scientific Advisory Committee and their annual meeting, including reporting back to all partners		X
4	Provide good communication between all partners, through a professional web site		X
5	Ensure timely and appropriate reporting to the commission and completion of deliverables in all Work Packages		X
6	Develop metrics to assess the progress of the grant and its impact on the BMS community	X	
7	Develop with all partners a plan for sustainability of the infrastructure built during the project, following completion of the grant		X
8	Ensure that ethics issues are addressed		X

3 Detailed report on the deliverable

3.1 Scope

3.1.1 Development and definition of metrics

The overall aim of this deliverable is to produce suitable metrics to track the progress and impact of the BioMedBridges project. A distinction must be made between metrics and performance metrics:

- a metric is a standard definition of any measurable quantity
- a performance metric is a standard definition of a measurable quantity that indicates some aspect of performance.

Performance metrics must have certain characteristics to be valuable and practical. They should:

- be measurable (or able to be determined indirectly from other measurements)
- have a clear definition, including limits and boundaries of the measurements
- indicate progress toward a performance goal/overall progress of the project
- contribute to answering specific questions about the performance and support decision making concerning directing efforts within the project or adjusting its aims.

In addition, (non-performance) metrics used for BioMedBridges should:

- enable the detection and documentation of what – in terms of technical solutions developed—works and what does not work
- document how RIs successfully “cluster”, i.e. move together and develop the common interfaces, technical infrastructure, and integration of the different scientific communities in order to enable metrics used for the

assessment of BioMedBridges to provide powerful arguments for the project and the participating research infrastructures.

The suggested metrics for the project fall into two groups:

1. Metrics showing overall project status, progress, visibility and impact
2. Technical metrics showing the development (progress) and usage (impact) of individual tools and services.

3.1.2 Rationale for metrics used in the project

Quality vs. quantity

Initial metrics for the project should be “inclusive”, i.e. it is better to collect all kinds of different data to begin with as long as they fulfil the basic requirements of feasibility and usefulness. An assessment of the suitability of different metrics must then be made once a sufficient body of data has been gathered to evaluate and decide on their relative effort and usefulness. This will likely be an ongoing effort as the project develops.

A complete list of metrics that may be considered—a “toolkit” of possible metrics—is included in Attachments 1 and 2 to this document.

Overall, a balance must be kept between the accuracy and timeliness of different metrics, their overall number, and their usefulness for the assessment of the project progress. In many cases, preliminary data and estimates may be sufficient to assess impact and make strategic decisions, so additional efforts to achieve more accurate measurements might be wasted.

Reporting frequency

Also important is due consideration of the frequency at which certain metrics are required or should be reported and the time frames used for assessment—for example, for web statistics/a counter showing data resources made available, continuous data collection is basically effortless; however, the evaluation of this

data may only be useful over larger time frames (e.g. months, years, or even project reporting periods).

In some instances the reporting frequency is driven by formal project requirements, for example reporting at the three-monthly meetings of the Executive Steering Committee of the project or the periodic reports to the Commission. Deciding which metrics—besides the standard project metrics (completion of deliverables etc.)—will be useful for inclusion in these reports will be part of the overall ongoing assessment of metrics.

3.1.3 Addressing project-wide issues

If developed and deployed appropriately, metrics used for the assessment of different parts of the BioMedBridges project may provide some necessary information that could contribute towards answering overarching questions in the technical/scientific domain and the science policy realm.

Technical/scientific domain

What is needed for scientific discovery? What do researchers want/need?

- For example: which services and resources are actually being used, and how much?

What are the use cases and real world problems?

- For example: how are the services and resources used? Are there emerging patterns?

What are the technical issues?

- For example: where do problems occur? Are there barriers to usage/usability?

Science policy domain

Does the project contribute to bringing the participating biomedical sciences research infrastructures (BMS RIs) closer together?

- For example: how did interactions develop from the baseline? Are there increased technical interactions, can synergies be identified and capitalised on?

Does the project provide increased visibility for the individual BMS RIs, or does it provide visibility to other stakeholders?

- For example: is the project (increasingly) being recognised and mentioned in different contexts, at different levels or by different communities? Is there an understanding of the project as a collaboration of the emerging BMS RIs?

3.2 Suggested metrics

The below provides an overview of the different areas in which metrics will be collected, together with the rationale or aims. Detailed information for metrics proposed for each area is provided in Attachment 1 (grant fulfilment, knowledge output and dissemination, outreach and inreach, training delivery) and Attachment 2 (technical metrics).

3.2.1 Grant fulfilment

The most basic project metrics are based on data from the necessary output and reporting for FP7 projects, such as the timely completion of deliverables and optimal use of resources. As these involve routine processes during grant management, the data for these metrics are readily available.

3.2.2 Technical metrics

BioMedBridges is a technical project that will produce tools and services. Metrics measuring their usability, usefulness, and usage/uptake are essential to ensure that the best possible solutions are developed for the researchers who will eventually use them.

The “users” of BioMedBridges will fall into two categories: service/data seekers and data/service providers. Metrics will be collected from both of these groups.

The technical metrics will assess data and services, standards and ontologies, and tools. A detailed matrix showing the different technical metrics and possible implementation at a high granularity is included in Attachment 2.

Data and services

Usage

Information on usage of data and services provided is necessary to ensure that the tools or functionality developed are those most needed by the research community. To collect the data, a complete list of the BioMedBridges services and tools (e.g. WP5 security portal, web service registry etc.) must be created and maintained.

- Among the most straightforward measures are website statistics such as hits, page impressions, web number of unique hosts, FTP unique IP addresses, and geographic distribution of IP addresses, all of which will provide easy and continuous information concerning the level of usage of publicly-facing information.
- The number and nature of queries and filters used in the different BioMedBridges web services and tools will provide insight into what users are looking for. When analysed, this can also identify gaps in the information provided or highlight misleading instructions.
- The number of links and referrals to services and resources using BioMedBridges portals will demonstrate how many links/bridges between different, related services have been created (and are being used).

A metric that would be highly desirable as it would provide insight into the scientific impact of the tools/data exposed/linked through BioMedBridges, but which is not currently feasible, is the number of hits for BioMedBridges services and data sources in Google Scholar and PubMed. This is due to two reasons:

1. There is no programmatic access to Google Scholar and is not reasonable to gather the data manually
2. There is (as yet), no standard way of referencing or attributing a dataset or service unless that dataset or service has already been published (in

which case the publication is cited – in such cases, if the PMID is provided with the dataset or service, counting the number of publications that reference these PMIDs would be feasible).

Use of tools

The complexity of measuring the use of tools depends on whether the tools are an exclusively BioMedBridges tool, whether BioMedBridges is contributing functionalities to an existing tool, or whether they are part of a shared development between BioMedBridges and other projects.

Mechanisms to track usage can be incorporated into the tool during development. Wherever possible, simple tools such as Google Analytics can and should be used to measure usage.

BioMedBridges enhancements to existing services: In the latter case, a distinction between the usage of the tool “with and without BioMedBridges” may be possible for example by incorporating an “advanced search” function to an existing search function or query mechanism that, if selected, would then feature BioMedBridges services. This would make the BioMedBridges impact on the tool traceable. A good example of a service for which this could be implemented would be MouseFinder¹, an existing service that will be enhanced by added BioMedBridges functionality.

Shared developments: In cases where tools or services are developed in collaboratively between BioMedBridges and another organisation or project (outside of BioMedBridges), a good mechanism to measure the impact of one or the other is not easily apparent. The measurement may simply capture the overall use of the resource, which would then have to be assessed in light of the relative contributions made by each project in each individual case.

¹www.mousemodels.org, MouseFinder: candidate disease genes from mouse phenotype data

Partner participation

The primary measure of participation by the partners in the technical developments of the project is the growth of each BioMedBridges tool or dataset in a given time frame based on, for example, the contributions made by partners to the tools themselves (e.g. number of services listed in the electronic service registry, see below under “Pilot study”) or the data resources that are made available (amount of data/size of datasets opened to BioMedBridges services).

Standards and ontologies

Adoption of (common) standards and data formats is integral to data sharing and the technical integration among the participating RIs. The metrics will provide a measure of the integration/uptake of data format and standards over different biomedical science domains.

Collection of data for metrics in this area will require relatively more effort as the WPLs will, in many cases, need to provide information on the standards and formats they use or have adopted. An example of a standards survey is included in Attachment 3. “Adoption of standards” can also be used as a technical metric to complement those intended to reflect “community integration” (see 3.2.4).

Ontologies developed/expanded and applied

Straightforward measures are available:

- Number of ontologies that have been developed or expanded due to efforts within BioMedBridges
- Number of datasets to which common data formats and/or ontologies have been applied due to efforts within BioMedBridges
- Number of BioMedBridges tools that leverage common data formats and/or ontologies that have been applied due to efforts within BioMedBridges.

Common data formats and standards established and applied

Again, the available measures are straightforward, including:

- Number of common data formats agreed and applied due to efforts within BioMedBridges
- Number of datasets to which common data formats and/or ontologies have been applied due to efforts within BioMedBridges
- Number of BioMedBridges tools which leverage common data formats and/or ontologies that have been applied due to efforts within BioMedBridges
- Number of common identifiers (e.g. the field "Gene ID") that occur in more than one dataset which is exposed or linked through BioMedBridges
- Number of datasets that have been integrated due to standards developed or applied through BioMedBridges.

Data provenance models established and adopted

Provenance describes the history of creation, modification and processes that influence data of interest. The existence or adoption of provenance models by the BioMedBridges partners is a measure for potential data interoperability and community integration in terms of data management.

While the number of tools in which a provenance model was adopted is a straightforward measure, the suggested description of the progress of data provenance models developed will take more effort both to collect and to analyse.

Tools

The key metrics in this area consist of the measurement of the availability and accessibility of core scientific resources provided by BioMedBridges, which must be monitored to ensure maximum possible use without "artificial" restrictions or constraints. Also among these metrics are the types of users who can access tools (e.g. by institution, authorization level, etc.) and level of access granted.

Release notes will provide a qualitative measure of new features, modifications developed and work performed on the different BioMedBridges tools.

Use case-specific metrics

Use-case specific metrics need to be tied to specific deliverables of the use case work packages. Since the majority of the use cases have not started as of the writing of this report, this process is foreseen to be finalised in year 2 of the project. A preliminary set of metrics has been identified and included in Attachment 2 to this report.

Pilot study

A number of the suggested technical metrics will be implemented in a service registry (eSR), which is one of the first tools to be developed within the project. This will serve as a pilot case to test feasibility of data collection and usefulness of each metric. Besides their use for tracking the progress of the eSR development itself, the metrics will be helpful in forming a comprehensive picture of the adoption of this first service by users and its usefulness to working bioinformaticians. This in turn will hugely assist informed decision making on the future tools and services to be developed within the project.

Three of the most important metrics to be tested with the eSR are:

- Usefulness/follow-up of user on resources provided will be measured via clicks of a “contact resource provider” button—this mechanism will provide data while keeping provider information relatively private
- The number of programmatic accesses will help decide where development effort should go (on the human or programmatic interface)
- The percentage of services registered in the eSR that are online and functional will provide insight into the availability of core BioMedBridges scientific resources.

3.2.3 Knowledge output and dissemination

Publications, citations, patents

Where possible, tools should be used to pull publication info. Publications can be identified via their acknowledgement of the grant. The data can also be used e.g.

to produce a regular list of publications, dissertations etc. that can be distributed to the partners or posted on the website.

A desirable metric would be the number of publications that are co-authored by two or more partners, as this might also provide a measure of collaboration and, if increasing over the course of the project, community integration as described in 3.2.4 below. However, there is currently no automated (or even semi-automated) way to put together such information. The feasibility of applying this metric is severely restricted by the fact that co-publications can currently only be detected by following this manual process:

1. Assemble a list of authors to be screened for co-publications
2. Generate a list of publications with their associated ID, for example from PubMed (PMID), against the author list
3. Screen for PMIDs that occur more than once (i.e. more than one author from the list is associated with the publication)
4. Check manually for false positives (caused by author ambiguity, i.e. more than one author with the same name in PubMed).

Under the given circumstances, the usefulness or even validity of the metric is also hampered by the fact that PubMed is not always comprehensive for the types of publications partners may have published or are publishing in. For example, it is conceivable in the context of the BioMedBridges project that there may be publications in specialised journals focussing on ethics or computer sciences, neither of which is covered by PubMed. Other questions arise when it comes to deciding who should be included in the list of authors to screen.

3.2.4 Outreach and inreach

Outreach and inreach for the project translate into two different areas in terms of metrics: project-internal interactions or community integration of the different biomedical sciences domains involved in the project (inreach) on one hand and interactions between the project or project partners and external parties and/or stakeholders (outreach) on the other.

Project-internal interactions (community integration)

Initially— for the first year of the project—simple linkages can be shown (i.e. “link exists” yes/no), such as for example collaboration of RIs and partners on deliverables and in WPs (see e.g. Figure 2). From the second year onwards, the (presumably changing) quality/type of linkage can be more closely monitored, e.g. the type and number of collaboration topics (e.g. ethics, secure access, intellectual property, standards, training, or other overarching topics).

Interactions between project/project partners and external parties

Metrics for outreach, dissemination activities and external relations are more straightforward. Activities can easily be assessed via data such as number of conferences and information events attended, project overview presentations given, number of external subscribers reached by BioMedBridges mailing lists, newsletters and news feeds (as applicable), number of press articles about the project, web stats.

For the latter, it may be interesting to also include search-engine based metrics and Google page rank (see <http://www.google.com/technology/>) (rank/relative improvement)². For example, the rank among “hits” for defined sets of search terms (e.g. “data sharing and personalised medicine”) could be monitored for possible relative improvement (i.e. higher ranks).

3.2.5 Training delivery and cross-RI workshops

The data that can easily be collected from the training activities of the project includes basic measures such as the number of training courses and course participants, the latter of which would be a measure of success of the courses and workshops.

Potentially very interesting data may also be collected on how much the training workshops contribute to the adoption of “best practices” at the different RIs with respect to e.g. data formats, standards, data provenance models etc. These data

²For suitability, see e.g. discussion in e-IRGSP2 deliverable D3.1 [Outreach and dissemination plan](#), page 10-11

can be collected by surveying course participants on the status quo before the workshop and in a follow-up after the workshop.

There is overlap with the technical metrics, which provides clear potential for useful feedback to the construction work packages.

3.3 Metrics as an incentive to data sharing

As pointed out by the initiators of the “Bioresource Research Impact Factor” (BRIF)³, besides technical and ethical aspects, a major obstacle for sharing resources such as data is the current absence of recognition for making the resource available. Metrics can provide an incentive to encourage data sharing. To achieve this, the metric (impact measure) should contribute to the data producer/contributor’s reputation.

Within the BioMedBridges project, this means in practice that mechanisms will be developed to show (real-time) information on the data made available within the project and the usage of the data. This could take the form of e.g. displaying the name, affiliation and data provided of the last partner contributing a resource on a web site, or providing a regularly (or real-time) updated list of overall contributors. Ideally, this will provide an incentive and encouragement to data providers and may lead to increased sharing.

To kick-start this process, the initial approach to this should be “quantity over quality” in terms of data made available. Later in the project, more attention must be paid to the types and suitability of the data.

³See: Cambon-Thomsen et al. (2011) The role of a bioresource research impact factor as an incentive to share human bioresources, *Nature Genetics* 43, 503–504, [doi:10.1038/ng.831](https://doi.org/10.1038/ng.831)

3.4 Other considerations

3.4.1 Collecting information

Some data is easily available, such as e.g. statistics for the project website at www.biomedbridges.eu (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Standard web site statistics for www.biomedbridges.eu (from publication of website in May to November 2012)

In other cases, acquiring data for metrics may require implementation of certain data collection mechanisms or tools. For example, tools needed to collect data on the usage, usefulness and usability of BioMedBridges services and resources might include:

- a tool to monitor the “up-time” and availability of a service
- a tool to collect feedback on the interest in/usefulness of a specific service or resource (e.g. “contact service provider” button as described above under 3.2.2 and in Attachment 1)

In general, the collection of data for metrics should be automated and “invisible” to the project partners – or, later, users of BioMedBridges resources – as much as possible so as not to impose an additional burden (or potential barrier with respect to the use of resources). Data for metrics should, ideally, be derivable from existing sources or mechanisms for gathering information. Metrics that would require measurements that are difficult to obtain should be avoided. Where either the metrics or their collection are “visible” and require effort from those involved, they should be easily understood and broadly accepted⁴.

In some cases, active input during data collection for metrics is necessary to get a more complete picture. For example, surveys may need to be deployed concerning the “connectedness” (inreach) metrics, to establish where or on which topics project partners are currently interacting with other project partners (i.e. getting a bottom line) and how this develops over the course of the project. Network analysis would be a useful tool to visualise such data; a baseline network analysis based on the number of project deliverables the BMS RIs are collaborating on is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Network analysis of BMS RIs showing collaboration within different work packages. Thicker lines (edges) represent a higher degree of overlap/larger number of work packages each pair of RIs collaborates in; proximity represents a higher degree of

⁴ See also “*Thinking Strategically: The Appropriate Use of Metrics for the Climate Change Science Program*”, Committee on Metrics for Global Change Research, Climate Research Committee, National Research Council. The National Academies Press, 2005, [p 50](#)

overlap between RIs on deliverables (larger number of shared deliverables). The graph was prepared using Gephi⁵.

3.4.2 Relative impact of resources

It is worth pointing out that some resources may be used by a comparatively small number of users, but there may be other measures that show the importance of the research. In contrast, resources in another area may have a lot of users, but comparatively less impact. Again in other cases, a resource may add significant value or be critical for another resource to run, but be invisible to an external user as such.

Any evaluation of different parts of the project should take this into account; metrics should always be viewed within the overall context of the project and the resources offered.

3.5 Next steps

Pilot study for technical metrics: Implement technical metrics (see Attachment 2) for service registry (eSR), test tools (WP4).

Collect baseline project metrics: Collect baseline for all metrics where feasible and appropriate (technical and other metrics).

Feedback from partners: Present the proposed metrics in a special session at the first Annual General Meeting (11-12 March 2012, Düsseldorf). Feedback from the partners will be collected and, if applicable, metrics adjusted accordingly. A final paper will then be produced for the first periodic project report.

Reporting: Once metrics are established, commence regular reporting of metrics to project management bodies.

Monitor and adjust metrics: Analyse data from initial metrics, evaluate usefulness, adjust if necessary (ongoing).

⁵ See: Bastian M., Heymann S., Jacomy M. (2009). *Gephi: an open source software for exploring and manipulating networks*. International AAAI Conference on Weblogs and Social Media; <https://gephi.org/>.

4 Publications

N/A

5 Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed: Yes No

6 Adjustments made

No adjustments were made to the deliverable. It should be noted that the Description of Work listed 1 person months planned effort from HMGU for this deliverable; however, the funds allocated per partner did not match this. The reporting here reflects the financial resources allocated to each partner. STFC contributed in-kind to this deliverable.

7 Efforts for this deliverable

Institute	Person-months (PM)		Period
	actual	estimated	
2: UOXF	0	0	July-December 2012
3: KI	1	1	July-December 2012
4: STFC	1	1	July-December 2012
5: UDUS	1	1 (listed under HMGU in DOW)	July-December 2012
13: VUMC	1	1	July-December 2012
Total	4		

Attachments

1. Metrics for grant fulfilment, knowledge output and dissemination, outreach and inreach, training delivery)
2. Overall technical and use case-specific metrics
3. Template for standards survey

Background information

This deliverable relates to WP 1; background information on this WP as originally indicated in the description of work (DoW) is included below.

WP 1 Title: Management
 Lead: Janet Thornton (EMBL)
 Participants: EMBL

The project will be coordinated by Professor Janet Thornton at EMBL-EBI. The management structure will consist of an Executive Steering Committee, made up of the coordinators of the individual ESFRI BMS projects, and a Technical Coordination Committee, consisting of the Chairs and Co-chairs of the work packages. Janet Thornton will chair both committees. The Technical Coordination Committee will report to the Coordinator and Executive Steering Committee on a regular basis.

Task 1: Overall Coordination of the project
 Task 2: Organisation of Management Meetings
 Task 3: Organisation of Scientific Advisory Board
 Task 4: Provision of a professional web site
 Task 6: Developing and monitoring progress and impact
 Task 7: Developing Sustainability Plan
 Task 8: Establish an Ethical Governance Committee

Work package number	WP1	Start date or starting event:		month 1		
Work package title		Management				
Activity Type		MGT				
Participant number	1:EMBL	2: UOXF	3: KI	4: STFC	11: HMGU	13: VUMC
Person-months per participant	48	0	1	1	1	1

Objectives

1. Manage the BioMedBridges project from Year 1-4
2. Organise the management meetings for all the project including: the Annual General Meeting for all partners; the Executive Steering Committee meetings (up to twice per annum) and the regular meetings of the Technical Coordination Committee (up to 3 times per annum)
3. Organise the Scientific Advisory Committee and their annual meeting, including reporting back to all partners
4. Provide good communication between all partners, through a professional web site
5. Ensure timely and appropriate reporting to the commission and completion of deliverables in all Work Packages
6. Develop metrics to assess the progress of the grant and its impact on the BMS community
7. Develop with all partners a plan for sustainability of the infrastructure built during the project, following completion of the grant
8. Ensure that ethics issues are addressed

Description of work and role of participants

The project will be coordinated by Professor Janet Thornton at EMBL-EBI. The management structure will consist of an Executive Steering Committee, made up of the coordinators of the individual ESFRI BMS projects, and a Technical Coordination Committee, consisting of the Chairs and Co-chairs of the work packages. Janet Thornton will chair both committees. The Technical Coordination Committee will report to the Coordinator and Executive Steering Committee on a regular basis.

Task 1: Overall Coordination of the project

The coordinator of BioMedBridges has full responsibility for managing this project and achieving its objectives, including infrastructure construction, project reporting and impact assessment and finance. The coordinator will be supported by a full time project manager, whose role will be to provide day-to-day support and implementation of all management and organisational tasks, including taking charge of accounting for all financial aspects of the project. The project manager will be responsible for the content management of the web site.

An Executive Steering Committee, consisting of all the coordinators of the 10 BMS Infrastructures, which are contributing to this grant. This committee, which is chaired by the BioMedBridges coordinator (who also coordinates the ELIXIR infrastructure), will play a strategic role in the management of the project and be responsible for decisions on the financial management. They will measure progress against the specific objectives, milestones and deliverables of each work package, developing metrics to measure the impact of the work. They will also ensure good coordination with the members of their own the infrastructure. They will oversee the consolidation of the data-infrastructure needs of the different projects, and develop a joint policy

on these issues. They will monitor the sustainability of the components of the infrastructure being developed and develop a plan for support following the completion of this grant. The Executive Board will meet twice in the first year: a kick-off meeting and an ordinary Board meeting. In subsequent years, there would be annual meetings, as well as conference calls every two to three months. It is anticipated that the meetings would be held in connection with the Annual General Meetings where possible.

The Technical Coordination Committee will comprise the coordinator of the grant and scientists in charge of different aspects of the construction work with responsibility for coordinating one work package (i.e. the chairs and co-chairs of the different construction Work Packages 1-5). The use case chairs will join this group as appropriate, during the tenure of their use case. This committee will therefore include Technical experts taken from each infrastructure. This Committee has the responsibility to assess and report to the Executive Steering Committee on the progress of the work packages and to identify and prioritise future tasks for the following year.

The chair for this committee will be the coordinator of the project. The Technical Coordination Committee will focus on the day-to-day and technical issues involved in achieving the planned deliverables and constructing the infrastructure. The Technical Coordination Committee will meet up to twice per year, in addition to the Annual General Meetings, and have monthly conference calls to deal with routine issues and resolve any urgent problems which may arise. The chairs and co-chairs of each Work Package will manage their own WP, ensuring good communication both within the WP and with the rest of this project, through this committee. This is described in more detail in the management section 2.1 below.

Task 2: Organisation of Management Meetings

The whole consortium will meet once a year at the Annual General Meetings. This Meeting will involve all the partners and those employed and working on the grant. Presentations will be made on progress on each work package and the use cases described. In the first year there will be an additional meeting at the start of the grant, to ensure good coordination from the beginning. The AGMs would also be the main opportunity for the Executive Board and the Technical coordination Committee to meet and take joint decisions on the direction of the project, and for the advisory bodies (see below) to learn about the project and the progress being made, as well as providing strategic advice. The last AGM will be an open meeting, in part to provide outreach to all the members of each infrastructure, and also to ensure good uptake and exploitation of the deliverables of BioMedBridges. This meeting will be coordinated by WP2.

Task 3: Organisation of Scientific Advisory Board

The project will have two advisory bodies. We will construct a Scientific Advisory Board, which will comprise a small number of experts in the biological and biomedical life science infrastructure area. This will include world class biologists, IT experts, ethical and legal experts. In addition, representatives of the large e-infrastructures will be invited to form a Technology Watch e-Advisory Task Force, to keep the project informed on developments in this field and in general guarantee a close association between the ICT e-infrastructures and this project. The e-Advisory Task Force will form the Technology Watch Work Package

(WP11), and consequently play a more integral part in the project than a conventional advisory board. It is anticipated that both advisory bodies would meet in connection with the Annual General Meetings.

Task 4: Provision of a professional web site

As well as providing the project with a public face, the project web site is also an important management tool. For this reason, the web site has been included in this work package, and will be based at EMBL-EBI, co-located with the coordinator and project manager. The internal/restricted part of the web site will be used both as a workplace and as a repository of documents. The task here is to provide the technical infrastructure for the website, whose contents will be controlled by the project manager.

Task 5: Reporting on the Project to Commission

The project coordinator will be responsible for reporting to the commission, with help from the project manager. Reports from each work package will be delivered by the chair of that work package to the project coordinator, who will then combine these reports to deliver a coordinated report.

Task 6: Developing and monitoring progress and impact

The management bodies will develop procedures and metrics at the beginning of the grant to measure the progress of the grant and its impact on the biological and medical research communities. These metrics will be reported annually. All the partners involved in this WP will have responsibility for this task.

Task 7: Developing Sustainability Plan

During the course of the project the executive steering committee will monitor the sustainability of the infrastructure under construction. All the partners involved in this WP will have responsibility for this task. In the last year of the project the executive steering Committee will report on the long term sustainability of each component delivered.

Task 8: Establish an Ethical Governance Committee which will:

- Provide an ethics management report to each meeting of BioMedBridges Executive Steering Committee
- Analyse the requirements from the Ethics Review Report
- Review the draft Ethical Governance Framework document Monitor the compliance of the project beneficiaries with the Ethical Governance Framework
- Prepare new versions of the Ethical Governance Framework for approval by the Executive Steering Committee
- Support the External Independent Ethics Advisor in the preparation of Progress of Compliance with Ethics Requirements Reports

Subcontracting for Audit Certificates: EMBL (Partner 1), STFC (Partner 4), UDUS (Partner 5), TUM-MED (Partner 7), TMF (Partner 10), HMGU (Partner 11), VUMC (Partner 13), UH (Partner 16).

Deliverables		
No.	Name	Due month
D1.1	Web Site (including meetings between the project manager, web developers and users, to develop the technical infrastructure and user experience of the projects public website)	12
D1.2	Devise Metrics to measure progress and impact of construction	12
D1.3	First Periodic Report (including the cost of hosting the Annual General Meeting; Executive Steering Committee meetings; SAB and Technology Watch e-Advisory Task Force meetings; Technical Coordination Committee meetings and the SAB chair's travel costs)	18
D1.4	Second Periodic Report (including the cost of hosting the Annual General Meeting; Executive Steering Committee meetings; SAB and Technology Watch e-Advisory Task Force meetings; Technical Coordination Committee meetings and the SAB chair's travel costs)	36
D1.5	Final Report & Sustainability Plan (including the cost of hosting the Annual General Meeting; Executive Steering Committee meetings; SAB and Technology Watch e-Advisory Task Force meetings; Technical Coordination Committee meetings and the SAB chair's travel costs)	48
D1.6	ED1: The Ethical Governance Framework for BioMedBridges (including the cost of holding Ethical Governance Committee meetings)	18
D1.7	ED2: Progress of Compliance with Requirements of the Ethics Review Report (including the cost of holding Ethical Governance Committee meetings)	36
D1.8	ED3: External Independent Ethics Advisors Report (Including cost of holding Ethical Governance Committee meetings)	48

Category	Progress or impact?	Metric	Unit/Criterion	Get data how?	Rationale	Difficulty/feasibility	Comments	Will collect data (NAME)
Basic project metrics								
Lead: Stephanie Suhr								
Grant fulfilment	Progress	Deliverables and milestones	met (on time, "of good quality")	reporting by project manager	Measures overall project progress; formal project requirement	Easy	Routine information; readily available.	Steffi Suhr
Grant fulfilment	Progress	Resources used	"Financial probity, funds must be properly distributed and accounted for and be in line with the budget"	reporting by project manager	Measures overall project progress; formal project requirement	Easy	Routine information; readily available.	Steffi Suhr
Grant fulfilment	Progress	Project meetings	Number of "Meetings ... held, attended by all partners and reported clearly"	reporting by project manager (with WPLs)	Measures overall project progress; formal project requirement	Easy	Routine information; readily available.	Steffi Suhr
Knowledge output and dissemination								
Lead: Stephanie Suhr								
knowledge output	Impact	Publications	Number of publications acknowledging grant	PubMed, Google Scholar	Demonstrates scientific output of project.	Easy	Currently no automated way to gather the information; metric relies on the grant being acknowledged in all pertinent publications.	Steffi Suhr
knowledge uptake	Impact	Publications	Type of publication/journal impact/open access in which grant output is published	PubMed, Google Scholar	Demonstrates scientific output of project.	Moderate	See above.	Steffi Suhr
knowledge output	Impact	Patents	Number of patents filed	Project manager collects from WPs	Demonstrates scientific output of project and translation of research results.	Easy		Steffi Suhr
Outreach and inreach								
Lead: Jan Willem Boiten								
Project-internal interactions (community integration)	Progress	Linkage between RIs	Participant lists from meetings/workshops to show links between infrastructures and partners (plot both)	Project manager collects from WPs	To show the development of community integration/connectivity and collaboration between the RIs	Easy	Relies on WPLs ensuring that complete participant lists are available and forwarded.	Steffi Suhr
Project-internal interactions (community integration)	Progress	Linkage between RIs	Collaboration of RIs and partners on Deliverables and in WPs, network analysis	Project manager collects	To show the development of community integration/connectivity and collaboration between the RIs	Moderate	Collection of data easy, data processing non-trivial.	Steffi Suhr
Project-internal interactions (community integration)	Progress	Collaboration topics	Type and number of (e.g. tools development, ethics, secure access, intellectual property, standards, training, other overarching topics)	Project manager collects with input from WPs	To show the development of community integration/connectivity and collaboration between the RIs	Moderate	Collection of data easy, data processing non-trivial.	Steffi Suhr
Project-internal interactions (community integration)	Progress	Linkage between RIs	Type/quality of linkage (network analysis)	Survey of BMS RIs; outreach WP	To show the development of community integration/connectivity and collaboration between the RIs	Moderate	Preparation of the survey needs some effort to develop useful/pertinent questions. Relies on survey buy-in and return.	NAME
Project-internal interactions (community integration)	Progress	Co-authorship	Number of co-publications (authors from different RIs), network graphs	- Assemble list of authors - Pull PMIDs for papers for that author from PubMed; clean duplicates - Assemble matrix (publications vs. authors) -> matches show co-authored papers	To show the development of community integration/connectivity and collaboration between the RIs	Very labour intensive	There is currently no automated (or even semi-automated) way to put together such information. Under the given circumstances, the usefulness or even validity of the metric is also hampered by the fact that PubMed is not always comprehensive for the types of publications partners may have published or are publishing in. Other questions arise when it comes to deciding who should be included in the list of authors to screen.	Steffi Suhr
Project-internal interactions (community integration)	Progress	Joint grant applications of RI/partner affiliates	Number of	WPL provide to project manager	To show the development of community integration/connectivity and collaboration between the RIs	Easy	Relies on WPLs providing timely information	Steffi Suhr
Dissemination	Impact	Presentations	Number of	Outreach WP with data from WPs	To demonstrate dissemination of information about the project and its outputs.	Easy	Relies on WPLs providing timely information	NAME
Dissemination	Impact	Presentations	Audience reached (type - e.g. lay, expert; size - e.g. less than 50, 50-100, >100)	Outreach WP with data from WPs	To demonstrate dissemination of information about the project and its outputs.	Easy	Relies on WPLs providing timely information	NAME

Category	Progress or impact?	Metric	Unit/Criterion	Get data how?	Rationale	Difficulty/feasibility	Comments	Will collect data (NAME)
External relations/interactions with external parties	Impact	Newsletter/newsfeed subscriptions	Number of external subscribers reached by BioMedBridges mailing lists, newsletters and news feeds	Outreach WP collects	Measure impact of and interest in the project and its outputs.	Easy	Readily available data (database of subscribers)	NAME
External relations/interactions with external parties	Impact	Media	Number of press articles/news items/blog posts about the project	Outreach WP collects	To demonstrate dissemination of information about the project and its outputs.	Easy	Readily available data; relies on WPLs contributing timely information. NOTE: this is also needed for reporting to Commission as well, so essential.	NAME
External relations/interactions with external parties	Impact	Information on website	Web hits per month	Web stats	Measure impact of and interest in the project and its outputs.	Easy	Analytics tool installed on website.	Outreach WP to collect
External relations/interactions with external parties	Impact	Information on website	Page impressions per month	Web stats	Measure impact of and interest in the project and its outputs.	Easy	Analytics tool installed on website.	Outreach WP to collect
External relations/interactions with external parties	Impact	Information on website	Web number of unique hosts per month	Web stats	Measure impact of and interest in the project and its outputs.	Easy	Analytics tool installed on website.	Outreach WP to collect
External relations/interactions with external parties	Impact	Search-engine based metrics	Google page rank/relative improvement	Outreach WP collects	Measure impact of and interest in the project and its outputs.	Easy	Google analytics	NAME
External relations/interactions with external parties	Impact	Search-engine based metrics	Rank among "hits" for defined set of search terms (e.g. "data sharing and personalised medicine")	WP2 compiles search terms; compile info on rank/relative improvement	Measure impact of and interest in the project and its outputs.	Moderate	Google analytics; some effort involved in the selection of suitable search terms.	NAME
External relations/interactions with external parties	Impact	Dissemination activities	Number of conferences and information events attended, project overview presentations given)	Outreach WP collects	Measure impact of and interest in the project and its outputs.	Easy	Relies on WPLs providing timely information. NOTE: this is also needed for reporting to Commission as well, so essential.	NAME
External relations/interactions with external parties	Impact	External funding leveraged	Amount of external funding or resources leveraged in the development of BioMedBridges resources	Project manager collects information from WPs	Shows collaboration with other projects and scientific communities outside of (but related to) BioMedBridges (e.g. TraIT).	Moderate	Some effort involved in identifying leveraged funding sources together with the WPLs.	NAME
Training delivery and cross-RI workshops Lead: Tom Hancocks/Cath Brooksbank								
Training delivery and cross-RI workshops	Impact	Training courses	Number of	WP12 collects.	Measure of impact of project; also a measure of community integration.	Easy	Information readily available.	Tom Hancocks
Training delivery and cross-RI workshops	Impact	Course participants	Number of	WP12 collects (workshop registrations).	Measure impact of project; also a measure of community integration.	Easy	Information readily available.	Tom Hancocks
Training delivery and cross-RI workshops	Impact	Course participants	Origin/affiliation of participants (by RI, country, institution, discipline)	WP12 collects (workshop registrations).	Measure impact of project; also a measure of community integration.	Easy	Information readily available.	Tom Hancocks
Training delivery and cross-RI workshops	Impact	Types of workshops held and developed	Number of	WP12 collects	Measure impact of and interest in the project and its outputs; demonstrate dissemination activities.	Easy	Information readily available.	Tom Hancocks
Training delivery and cross-RI workshops	Impact	Adoption of best practices: data formats, standards, data provenance models (also see technical metrics; can serve as measure for community integration)	Number of	WP12 conducts pre-workshop survey, post-workshop follow-up	Measure for community integration and uptake of project output.	Moderate	Some effort involved in developing survey; relies on survey return from participants.	Tom Hancocks
Training delivery and cross-RI workshops	Impact	Uptake of workshops at RIs	See number of training courses, course participants	WP12 collects.	Measure for community integration and uptake of project output.	Moderate	Some effort involved in developing survey; relies on survey return from participants.	Tom Hancocks

Group	Progress/ Impact	Metric	Tools impacted	Unit	Rationale	Frequency	Manual / Automated	Effort to establish	Effort to sustain	Mechanism	Notes	Contact
Data and services	Impact	Usage	All BMB webpages and webapps	Number of BMB webpages and webapps (e.g. WP5 security portal, web service registry etc.)	We need to maintain a list of BMB webpages and webapps, if for no other reason than to know what we need to collect metrics on.	Monthly	Manual	Difficult	Moderate	Manually curated list.	Non-trivial, but absolutely required to ensure completeness of metrics collection. Will need to develop a "standard" for analytics (i.e. what is included, which data is essential). Also need to determine which pages should be included.	Julie McMurphy
Data and services	Impact	Usage	All BMB webpages and webapps	Web hits	Provides easily available and continuous information concerning the level of usage of publicly-facing information	Monthly	Semi-automatic	Easy-Moderate	Easy	Google Analytics	Gathering raw data access is quite easy. Devising a reasonable summary of all pages, or key information may take some thinking.	Julie McMurphy
Data and services	Impact	Usage	All BMB webpages and webapps	Page impressions	Provides easily available and continuous information concerning the level of usage of publicly-facing information	Monthly	Semi-automatic	Easy-Moderate	Easy	Google Analytics	Gathering raw data access is quite easy. Devising a reasonable summary of all pages, or key information may take some thinking.	Julie McMurphy
Data and services	Impact	Usage	All BMB webpages and webapps	Web number of unique hosts	Provides easily available and continuous information concerning the level of usage of publicly-facing information	Monthly	Semi-automatic	Easy-Moderate	Easy	Google Analytics	Gathering raw data access is quite easy. Devising a reasonable summary of all pages, or key information may take some thinking.	Julie McMurphy
Data and services	Impact	Usage	All BMB webpages and webapps	FTP unique IP addresses	Provides easily available and continuous information concerning the level of usage of publicly-facing information	Monthly	Semi-automatic	Easy-Moderate	Easy	Google Analytics	Gathering raw data access is quite easy. Devising a reasonable summary of all pages, or key information may take some thinking.	Julie McMurphy
Data and services	Impact	Usage	All BMB webpages and webapps	Geographic distribution of IP addresses	Provides easily available and continuous information concerning the level of usage of publicly-facing information	Monthly	Semi-automatic	Easy-Moderate	Easy	Google Analytics	Gathering raw data access is quite easy. Devising a reasonable summary of all pages, or key information may take some thinking.	Julie McMurphy
Data and services	Impact	Usage	All BMB webpages and webapps	Number and nature of queries & filters	Provides insight into what users are looking for. When analyzed, this can also identify gaps in information provided or misleading instructions.	Monthly	Semi-automatic	Easy-Moderate	Easy	Programmatic mechanisms will vary by site. Results will be logged monthly and manually analyzed quarterly.	Difficulty will vary by site / application	Julie McMurphy
Data and services	Impact	Partner Participation	BMB tools & datasets	Growth of each such dataset each month, Contributions to registry each month	Provides insight into growth of core BMB scientific resources.	Monthly - Quarterly	Semi-automatic	Easy-Moderate	Easy	Programmatic mechanisms will vary by dataset; the unit of data may vary from dataset to dataset	Simple for registered services, more difficult for datasets	Julie McMurphy
Data and services	Impact	Usage	eSR	Clicks of "Contact resource provider" button	Indicates usefulness/follow-up while protecting provider contact info from being scraped by bots.	Monthly	Semi-automatic	Easy-Moderate	Easy	Google Analytics; programmatic logs	Gathering raw data access is quite easy. Devising a reasonable summary of all pages, or key information may take some thinking.	Julie McMurphy
Data and services	Impact	Usage	eSR	Number of programmatic accesses	Helps decide where development effort should go (on human or programmatic interface)	Monthly	Semi-automatic	Easy-Moderate	Easy	Programmatic logs	Straightforward	Julie McMurphy
Data and services	Impact	Availability (online and functional)	eSR	Percentage of registered services that are online/functional for a given month.	Provides insight into availability of core BMB scientific resources. Measures accessibility of tools - this must be monitored to ensure maximum possible use without "artificial" restrictions or constraints.	Monthly	Semi-automatic	Easy-Moderate	Easy	eGI monitoring tool? Biocatologue monitoring tool?	Functional testing, while highly desirable, hinges on the willingness of the developer to contribute a test script. Historically this is a hard sell.	Julie McMurphy
Data and services	Impact	Usage	eSR (Webservices and Datasets listed therein)	Hits in Google Scholar	This information is desirable as it provides insight into the scientific impact of the tools/data exposed/linked through BMB.	Baseline and yearly	Manual	Difficult	Difficult	Google	Not feasible: There is no programmatic access to Google Scholar and we can not do this manually. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Google_Scholar	Julie McMurphy
Data and services	Impact	Usage	eSR (Webservices and Datasets listed therein)	Hits in PubMed Central	This information is desirable as it provides insight into the scientific impact of the tools/data exposed/linked through BMB.	Baseline and yearly	Manual	Difficult	Easy	Text mining program TBD	While not difficult per se, this would be a time consuming program to develop and success would not be guaranteed. There is (as yet), no standard way of referencing or attributing a dataset or service except if that dataset or service is already published. In such cases, if the PMID is provided with the dataset or service, counting the number of publications that reference these PMIDs would be feasible.	Julie McMurphy
Data and services	Impact	Usage	BMB tools & datasets	Number of clicks through to services and resources from BMB portals	Demonstrates how many links/bridges between different, related services have been created (and are being discovered through BMB).	Quarterly	Semi-automatic	Easy-Moderate	Easy	Google Analytics	Requires other services to add Google Analytics widget. An example for this would be UniProf?	
Standards	Progress	Ontologies developed / expanded	BMB tools & datasets	Number of common data formats agreed upon and/or ontologies developed or expanded due to BMB	Constitutes a measure of the integration/uptake of standards over different BMS domains.	Baseline and yearly	Manual	Easy-Moderate	Easy-Moderate	Information must be provided by WPs/partners (via regular survey).		Julie McMurphy
Standards	Progress	Data provenance models established	BMB tools & datasets	Description of the progress of data provenance models developed	Measure for potential data interoperability and community integration in terms of data management	Baseline and yearly	Manual	Easy-Moderate	Easy	Manual Paragraph(?) summary from WP3	Not automatic, but not difficult	Julie McMurphy
Standards	Progress	Common ontologies applied	BMB datasets	Number of datasets to which common ontologies have been applied due to BMB	Constitutes a measure of the integration/uptake of data format and standards over different BMS domains.	Baseline and yearly	Manual	Difficult	Difficult	Information must be provided by WPs/partners (via regular survey).	Moderately difficult to execute and summarize across datasets.	Julie McMurphy
Standards	Progress	Common formats applied	BMB datasets	Number of datasets to which dataformat standards have been applied due to BMB	Constitutes a measure of the integration/uptake of data formats over different BMS domains.	Baseline and yearly	Manual	Difficult	Difficult	Information must be provided by WPs/partners (via regular survey).	Moderately difficult to execute and summarize across datasets.	Julie McMurphy

Group	Progress/ Impact	Metric	Tools impacted	Unit	Rationale	Frequency	Manual / Automated	Effort to establish	Effort to sustain	Mechanism	Notes	Contact
Standards	Impact	Common ontologies applied	BMB tools	Number of BMB tools which leverage common ontologies due to BMB	Constitutes a measure of the integration/uptake of data format and standards over different BMS domains.	Baseline and yearly	Manual	Difficult	Difficult	Information must be provided by WPs/partners (via regular survey).	Moderately difficult to execute and summarize across datasets.	Julie McMurry
Standards	Impact	Common data formats applied	BMB tools	Number of BMB tools which leverage common data formats due to BMB	Constitutes a measure of the integration/uptake of standards over different BMS domains.	Baseline and yearly	Manual	Difficult	Difficult	Information must be provided by WPs/partners (via regular survey).	Moderately difficult to execute and summarize across datasets.	Julie McMurry
Standards	Impact	Common identifiers applied	BMB datasets	Number of common types of identifiers that occur in datasets exposed or linked through BMB. (I.e. is there a field for e.g. Uniprot ID, Gene ID, etc. in more than one database?)	This will provide a measure of the potential of datasets to be linked together, even if they are not linked yet.	Baseline and yearly	Manual	Difficult	Difficult	Programmatic mechanisms will vary by dataset.	Moderately difficult to execute and summarize across datasets. Can pilots (to test feasibility) be identified within the use cases?	Julie McMurry
Standards	Impact	Data provenance models adopted	BMB tools	Number of tools in which the provenance model was adopted	Measure for data interoperability and community integration in terms of data management	Baseline and yearly	Manual	Moderate	Moderate	Survey?	Moderately difficult	Julie McMurry
Tools	Impact	Data and tool accessibility	BMB tools & datasets	Types of users who can access tools (Maybe by institution, authorization level, etc) and level of access granted	Provides insight into availability of core BMB scientific resources. Measures accessibility of tools - this must be monitored to ensure maximum possible use without "artificial" restrictions or constraints.	Baseline and yearly	Manual	Moderate	Moderate	Survey?	Moderately difficult. The effort to integrate data is of little use if the access to it is unnecessarily restricted.	Julie McMurry
Tools	Impact	Usage	BMB tools & datasets	Number of users of an exclusively BioMedBridges tool	Necessary to develop tools or functionality in tools that are most needed by the research community.	Quarterly	Semi-automatic	Moderate	Moderate	Mechanism to capture use built into tool, e.g. Google Analytics		
Tools	Impact	Usage	BMB tools & datasets	Number of users of an existing tool that is enhanced by BioMedBridges functionality	Necessary to develop tools or functionality in tools that are most needed by the research community.	Quarterly	Semi-automatic	Moderate	Moderate	E.g. "advanced search" function added to existing search or query that unlocks the BioMedBridges services; then measure usage of this functionality (e.g. Google Analytics)	Feasible for existing resources such as e.g. emb, MouseFinder.	
Tools	Progress	Jira tickets (issue tracking in tools development)	BMB tools	The quantifiable measure is number of Jira tickets closed.	Will measure the progress in tools development.	Quarterly	Semi-automatic	Easy	Easy	Jira reporting tools	While some tickets are larger than others, closing more is always better than closing fewer. It gives a very rough estimate of work volume. Easy to retrieve this data from Jira, but not automatically pushable to a metrics website	Julie McMurry
Tools	Progress	Software release notes	BMB tools	Release notes: The qualitative measure is the number of new features or modifications developed.	Release notes provide a human readable, succinct summary of work performed. Because of Agile methodologies, the work should easily map to objectives that users iteratively identify.	Quarterly	Manual	Moderate	Moderate	Manual summary	Not automatic, but not difficult	Julie McMurry
Use cases	Progress	PM data access requests	Process specification for secure sharing of and access to PM data	Number of data access requests formally submitted	Provides a measure of the amount of background data collected for the process specification	biannually	Manual	Easy	Easy	Manual review	WP8	Imre Vastrik, Henrik Edgren
Use cases	Impact	Functionality of software	Software to estimate the probability of various conformations, their hydrated volumes and shapes and the average hydrated volume								WP9	Martyn Winn
Use cases	Impact	Functionality of web service	Web-service for segmentation and identification of components in volume data								WP9	Martyn Winn
Use cases	Impact	Data elements mapped	Mapping between data elements	Number of data elements mapped							WP9	Martyn Winn
Use cases	Impact	Phenotypic terms used in healthcare linked to genomic information (e.g. gene identifiers)	Prototype linking ICD10/SNOMED CT concepts to Ensembl gene identifiers	Number of phenotypic terms used in healthcare linked to genomic information (e.g. gene identifiers)							WP10	Alvis Brazma
Use cases	Impact	Extent of bridging between public resources and biobanks	BioSamples database, Biobank sample access systems	Number of samples linked from public repositories (BioSamples) to biobanks	Demonstrates how sample availability information in biobanks can be published and linked	Quarterly	Semi-automatic	Easy-Moderate	Easy	Query in the BioSamples database	WP10	Alvis Brazma
Use cases	Impact	List of standards and ontologies in cellular image data sets	Cellular image data sets	Number of standards and ontologies captured	Necessary for data integration and development of interoperability tools.	Baseline	Manual	Easy-Moderate	Easy	Information will be manually curated by WP partners	WP6	Tanja Ninkovic
Use cases	Impact	List of standards and ontologies in mouse image data sets	Mouse image data sets	Number of standards and ontologies captured	Necessary for data integration and development of interoperability tools.	Baseline	Manual	Easy-Moderate	Easy	Information will be manually curated by WP partners	WP6	Tanja Ninkovic
Use cases	Impact	List of standards and ontologies in human image data sets	Human image data sets	Number of standards and ontologies captured	Necessary for data integration and development of interoperability tools.	Baseline	Manual	Easy-Moderate	Easy	Information will be manually curated by WP partners	WP6	Tanja Ninkovic
Use cases	Impact	Mapping of standards and ontologies between the different image reference data sets	Image reference data sets	Number of standards and ontologies mapped	Measure of progress of interoperability standards	Baseline	Semi-automatic	Difficult	Difficult	Automatic or manual intervention will be implemented as needed.	WP6	Tanja Ninkovic

Group	Progress/ Impact	Metric	Tools impacted	Unit	Rationale	Frequency	Manual / Automated	Effort to establish	Effort to sustain	Mechanism	Notes	Contact
Use cases	Impact	Predicted biomarkers	Image reference data sets	Number of predicted biomarkers	Measure of the usefulness of the interoperability standards	Baseline	Automatic	Moderate	Easy	Programs will be implemented that take advantage of the interoperability standards	WP6	Tanja Ninkovic
Use cases	Impact	Co-annotated mouse-human datasets	Mouse-human datasets	Number of co-annotated datasets	A reasonable amount of data is necessary	Baseline	Automatic	Easy-Moderate	Easy	Datasets will be curated manually	WP7	Philip Gormanns
Use cases	Impact	Linkage of mouse-human datasets	Mouse-human datasets	Network characteristic of mouse-human co-annotated datasets	Measure the value of the datasets and describe their linkage properties	Baseline	Automatic	Moderate-Difficult	Easy	Manual selection of appropriate algorithms and network metrics	WP7	Philip Gormanns
Use cases	Impact	Functionality of tools for mouse-human phenotype matches	Sample discovery tool for mouse-human phenotype matches	Percentage of accurate matches	Performance measure for the developed classifier (Recall, Precision, F-measure...)	Baseline	Automatic	Easy	Easy	Automatic validation step during classifier development	WP7	Philip Gormanns
Security	Impact	Functionality and user uptake	Tool for assessment of regulatory and ethical requirements; including supportive documents	Number of users and user satisfaction							WP5	Someone from TMF
Security	Impact	Functionality and user satisfaction	Security framework								WP5	Klaus Kuhn

BioMedBridges STANDARDS metric v0.3

	<i>Use-cases</i>				
	WP6 <i>Interoperability of large scale image data sets from different biological scales</i>	WP7 <i>PhenoBridge - crossing the species bridge between mouse and human</i>	WP8 <i>Personalized Medicine</i>	WP9 <i>From cells to molecules-integrating structural data</i>	WP10 <i>Integrating disease related data and terminology from samples of different types</i>
BMS RI					
BBMRI	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TRUE	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TRUE		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TRUE
EATRIS	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TRUE		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TRUE		
ECRIN			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TRUE		
ELIXIR	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TRUE	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TRUE	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TRUE	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TRUE	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TRUE
Euro-Biomed	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TRUE				
Infrafrontier	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TRUE	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TRUE			
INSTRUCT		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TRUE		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TRUE	
Number of participating RI's	4	4	4	2	2
Standards					
MAGE-TAB (MicroArray Gene Expression Tabular)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE	<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE		<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE
XGAP (eXtensible Genotype And Phenotype) format		<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE	<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE		<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE
Observe-OM		<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE	<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE		<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE
VCF (Variant Call Format)	<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE	<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE	<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE		<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE
BAM (Binary sequence Alignment/Map format)	<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE	<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE	<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE		<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE
EMDB Map Format (Electron Microscopy Data Bank)	<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE	<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE	<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE	<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE	<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE
PDB (Protein Data Bank format)		<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE		<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE	
Mass Spec XML e.g. mzXML, mzDATA, mzML		<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE		<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE	
Copy number variations in bedgraph and custom tabular formats	<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE		<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE		
FASTA format for nucleotide/peptide sequences	<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE		<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE		
HL7 standards			<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE		
CDISC standards	<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE		<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE		
SNOMED			<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE		
ICD standards			<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE		
MedDRA (Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities)			<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE		
LOINC (Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes)			<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE		
BRIDG (Biomedical Research Integrated Domain Group model)			<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE		
PCROM (Primary Care Research Object Model)			<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE		
ISO/IEC 11179			<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE		
SEND (Standard for Exchange of Non-clinical Data)			<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE		
DICOM (Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine)	<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE		<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE		
AIM XML (Annotation and Image Markup)	<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE				
MP ontology (Mammalian Phenotype)	<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE	<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE			
mmCIF dictionaries (macromolecular Crystallographic Information File)		<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE		<input type="checkbox"/> FALSE	
Number of standards covered	0	0	0	0	0
Number of relevant standards	9	10	19	4	6